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Study on the Transformation of Young Volunteers from Applied Undergraduate Colleges to Social Entrepreneurs in Zhejiang Province

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Abstract

With the development of social public welfare undertakings, the requirements for public welfare personnel are getting higher and higher. In order to engage in public welfare undertakings better and longer, the transformation of young college student volunteers to social entrepreneurs is becoming more and more prominent. In view of this, through qualitative methods, this study explores the supporting theory of the transformation, analyzes the relevant influencing factors of the transformation of applied undergraduate college students volunteers to social entrepreneurs, explores the typical cases of the transformation of young college students to social entrepreneurs in China, and adopts the perspective of college students and problem-oriented thinking. It innovatively proposes the transformation path and countermeasures for young volunteers in applied undergraduate colleges in Zhejiang Province to become social entrepreneurs, hoping to enrich the transformation theory of young volunteers from college students to social volunteers and provide theoretical basis for the smooth transformation of applied undergraduate volunteers into social entrepreneurs.

Keywords: Social Entertainment, College Students Volunteer Service, Transformation Path

1. Introduction

In the new era, China's rapid economic and social development and the continuous improvement of the rule of law have put forward higher requirements for society. The report to the 20th CPC National Congress made it clear that high-quality development should be promoted, and stressed the importance of innovation and entrepreneurship. With the diversification and complexity of social needs, training young people with innovative capabilities and practical experience in public interest entrepreneurship has become an important issue for social development. In this context, as an important force for social service, how to transform college student volunteers from the traditional model of volunteer service to the leader of social entrepreneurship has become the focus of social attention. Therefore, this study puts forward the research topic of the path and countermeasures of the transition from college volunteers to social entrepreneurs.

The significance of social entrepreneurship lies in maximizing social value through innovation and entrepreneurship; The significance of volunteerism is to promote social harmony and cultivate the sense of civic responsibility and social participation; The significance of the transformation of the two is to promote the transformation of volunteer groups into more influential and sustainable social entrepreneurs, so as to provide more effective and sustainable social services to the society.

However, in the process of transforming college volunteers into social entrepreneurs, they still face the following problems: First, college volunteers lack the knowledge and skills of social entrepreneurship, which makes it difficult for them to effectively complete the transition from volunteer to entrepreneur; Secondly, social support policies and resources for social entrepreneurs are limited, especially in the initial stage of entrepreneurship, which makes it difficult for entrepreneurs to obtain sufficient resources and financial support; Third, the sustainability of social entrepreneurship faces challenges. Some social entrepreneurship projects are difficult to achieve long-term development, leading to setbacks for entrepreneurs in the implementation process.

To sum up, in view of the current status and difficulties encountered by college volunteers in their transition to social entrepreneurship, we will focus on the following issues:

- 1) What is the theoretical basis for the transformation of college volunteers into social entrepreneurs? What factors have been identified as key transformation factors in the existing research?
- 2) In actual cases, what are the key success factors for college volunteers to transform into social entrepreneurs? What specific practices have a direct impact on the transformation?

Figure 1: Correspondence between research questions and research methods

2. Literature review

2.1 Concepts of youth volunteerism and social entrepreneurship

In terms of summarizing the main research results, scholars have achieved certain results in their research on the transformation of young college student volunteers into social entrepreneurs. First of all, with regard to the concept of the two, social entrepreneurship, as an emerging social phenomenon, has attracted wide attention in recent years. Shuo Zhang, Huaixin Zhu, Jihai Lu and Meili Lu (2023) believe that the concept of social entrepreneurship involves developing ethical leaders through stages of concept construction, ethical conflict, relationship building and rule-making with the help of social entrepreneurship education. social entrepreneurship refers to the behavior of individuals or organizations that adopt innovative methods and technologies to solve social problems in the process of pursuing the maximization of social value. It not only contains the characteristics of innovation, opportunity orientation and growth in the traditional sense of entrepreneurship, but also emphasizes the concern and improvement of social welfare. Regarding the basic concept of youth volunteerism, Valeriia Ovcharova Ganna Boiko Mariia Kulyk (2023) proposes youth volunteerism as a social technology that engages young people in public activities and influences their career strategies. It involves active participation in various volunteering activities for the benefit of society and personal growth. Youth volunteerism, according to the Regulations on Voluntary Service promulgated by The State Council of China, refers to the public services provided by volunteers,

voluntary service organizations and other organizations voluntarily and without compensation to society or others. Youth volunteerism refers especially to such activities in which young people participate. It has the characteristics of voluntary, gratuitously, public welfare and organization. By contributing their time and energy, young volunteers provide services to society and promote social progress.

2.2 The relationship between youth volunteering and social entrepreneurship

Regarding the relationship between volunteer service and social entrepreneurship, Zhang Xiaoyan and Chen Wanming (2018) pointed out that volunteer service is an important foundation for social entrepreneurship, which can cultivate college students' sense of social responsibility and service awareness and lay a solid foundation for subsequent social entrepreneurship activities. At the same time, they also put forward a specific path for the transformation from volunteering to social entrepreneurship, including key links such as improving personal ability, building a team, and finding resources. Erhan ACAR and Nilgun OZCAN (2022) propose that there is a positive correlation between youth volunteering motivation and social entrepreneurship propensity, suggesting a link between altruistic actions and innovative solutions to meet social needs. This also proves that there is a strong link between volunteerism and social entrepreneurship. On the one hand, volunteering can be a starting point for social entrepreneurship. Many social entrepreneurs start out by volunteering, gradually identifying social problems and seeking sustainable solutions. On the other hand, in her article, Nadiiya discusses youth participation in volunteering and social entrepreneurship during the crisis, highlighting support for youth in difficult situations and its role in charitable activities. social entrepreneurship, in turn, can provide a broader space for volunteering and a more permanent support mechanism. For example, Fan Youzhen and Yang Mengting (2022) point out that through social entrepreneurship, volunteering activities can be transformed into a long-term and sustainable social service model, providing more resources and impetus for solving social problems. The transformation of young volunteers into social entrepreneurs can not only promote personal growth and development, but also bring about positive changes in society. First, on a personal level, the transformation helps to enhance young people's sense of social responsibility and mission. Fan Youzhen and Yang Mengting (2022) pointed out in their research that by participating in social entrepreneurship activities, young volunteers can combine their professional knowledge with social needs to creatively solve social problems, thus achieving both self-worth and social value. Secondly, at the social level, social entrepreneurship can stimulate more social innovation vitality and promote social progress. Research shows that young volunteers in the process of social entrepreneurship can attract more people to pay attention to and participate in social welfare undertakings, forming a good social atmosphere. In addition, the relationship between volunteerism and social entrepreneurship is also reflected in their joint role in promoting social innovation. To sum up, the relationship between volunteering and social entrepreneurship is mutually reinforcing. Volunteering provides a wealth of practical experience and a broad social foundation for social entrepreneurship, while social entrepreneurship brings broader prospects and development opportunities for volunteering. Therefore, it is of great practical significance to explore the internal relationship between the two in-depth to promote the development of China's public welfare undertakings.

2.3 The transformation path of youth volunteering and social entrepreneurship

A number of literatures have pointed out that volunteer service experience is an important basis for young volunteers to transform into social entrepreneurship. For example, the Report on China Youth social entrepreneurship shows that many young social entrepreneurs came up with the idea of starting a business because they found social problems in volunteering projects. These volunteer service activities are mainly in areas such as education for left-behind children in rural areas, disaster prevention and mitigation education, legal aid for vulnerable groups, and voluntary help for vulnerable groups. In their research, Zhang Xiaoyan and Chen Wanming (2018) emphasized the path of transformation from college students' volunteer service to social entrepreneurship. They believed that the main obstacles to be overcome in the transformation process included fundraising, project sustainability, and social recognition. However, once the transformation is successfully achieved, it can effectively promote the improvement of social well-being. Take the "Human Fireworks" project as an example. The project has moved from a simple volunteer service to a public welfare venture. It has gradually explored ways of effective operation and self-creation by raising financial resources through multiple ways, planting fruits and vegetables to meet the needs of critically ill patients, and providing differentiated services to different target groups. At the same

time, the project still maintains the volunteer service of care and help for the families of special patients with severe diseases, realizing the organic combination of social entrepreneurship and volunteer service. Khadijah Alavi (2022) explores how youth volunteerism can be transformed into social entrepreneurship to provide valuable services to the elderly. The potential of harnessing youth in aged care through a profit-oriented approach to volunteering is drawn. To sum up, the specific path for young volunteers to transform into social entrepreneurship includes many aspects, such as clarifying transformation goals and directions, formulating detailed plans, building platforms and integrating resources, implementing and operating, expanding and replicating, and maintaining original aspirations and responsibilities. Through the implementation of these paths, young volunteers can successfully transform volunteer services into social entrepreneurship projects and make more contributions to society.

3. Research methods

3.1 Literature research method

What is the theoretical basis for the transformation of college volunteers into public interest entrepreneurs? What factors have been identified as the key transformation factors in the existing research?

In order to investigate this question, this study searched about 200 relevant literatures through objective sampling and Chinese and foreign academic databases such as Web of Science, Google Scholar and CNKI, and retained about 100 literatures on young university student volunteers and social entrepreneurship through preliminary screening of titles and abstracts. Through in-depth reading and analysis of the selected literature, key concepts, theories, models and cases were extracted. Identify recurring themes and patterns in the literature that may point to key elements of college student youth volunteers and social entrepreneurs. Analyze the interactions and dependencies between the key elements and reveal their internal connections.

In the course of further reading and analysis, we focus on the following aspects:

- 1) The relevance of volunteerism and social entrepreneurship: Analyze how volunteerism provides practical experience and social capital for social entrepreneurship.
- 2) Factors affecting the transformation of volunteers: Explore the influence of personal characteristics (such as social responsibility, innovative spirit), social support system (such as policies, resources) and other factors on the transformation process.
- 3) Educational background and willingness to start a business: Study the influence of college student's educational experience, especially entrepreneurship education and volunteer service education, on their willingness to start a public business.

3.2 Case study

What are the key success factors for a college student volunteer to become a social entrepreneurs in a real case? What specific practices have had a direct impact on the transition?

In order to explore the specific path and key success factors of the transformation of college volunteers into public interest entrepreneurs, this study selected the "Youth Red Dream Building Journey Track in China International 'Internet Plus' College Students Innovation and Entrepreneurship Competition" as a typical case to conduct in-depth research. The competition is one of the most influential college student innovation and entrepreneurship competitions in China. Among them, the "Youth Red Dream Journey" track focuses on social entrepreneurship projects, aiming to guide college students to combine innovation and entrepreneurship with social service, and realize the unity of personal value and social value. Case selection criteria: a) Typicality of cases: We selected those projects that performed well in the competition, were innovative and had a social impact. b) Diversity of cases: Ensure that the selected projects cover different types of social entrepreneurship, such as education and poverty alleviation, environmental protection, community services, etc. c) Data availability: We selected cases where there is a wealth of information in public literature and reports, and where the project team is willing to provide further interview or research opportunities.

Case: As a unique competition that integrates red culture, innovation and entrepreneurship and rural revitalization, the track of "Youth Red Dream Journey" in the China International "Internet Plus" College Student Innovation and Entrepreneurship Competition is self-evident in its far-reaching significance. This track actively responds to the national rural revitalization strategy and targeted poverty alleviation policy, encourages young students to integrate their passionate youth dreams into the grand blueprint of national development, through the means of public welfare innovation and entrepreneurship, go deep into the old revolutionary base areas and poor areas, face the practical challenges of agricultural, rural and urban and rural community development, and strive to solve the pain points at the same time, To realize the double leap of economic value and social value. On this track, there is a wide range of project types, covering many frontier fields such as modern agriculture, smart agriculture, intelligent agricultural machinery and equipment, agricultural big data and leisure agriculture, aiming to use new technologies and models to promote rural industrial upgrading and community development. With enthusiasm and innovative spirit, the participating teams are set up across schools and go hand in hand to constantly sharpen their will and improve their capabilities in the fierce competition. They are open to registered or unregistered projects, but emphasize the participation and responsibility of students as core members of the project to ensure the authenticity and sustainability of the project.

The "Youth Red Dream Journey" track also actively advocates the participation of young college student volunteers, and integrates the transformation of social entrepreneurship into the practice of innovation and entrepreneurship. The young students went into the old revolutionary base areas, not only to experience the revolutionary spirit and strengthen their ideals and beliefs, but also to translate this spiritual power into practical actions, and bring real changes to the local areas through social entrepreneurship projects. Using the new generation of information technologies such as mobile Internet, cloud computing, big data, artificial intelligence and the Internet of Things, they contributed wisdom and strength to targeted poverty alleviation and rural revitalization, while accumulating valuable experience for their own growth and development.

The "Youth Red Dream Journey" track has not only achieved a large number of excellent innovative and entrepreneurial projects, but also provided valuable practical opportunities and growth platforms for young students. The implementation of these projects has not only promoted the prosperity of the rural economy and the development of communities, but also strengthened the contact and cooperation between colleges and local governments, enterprises and other social sectors, promoted the deep integration of industry, university and research, and injected new vitality and impetus into the rural revitalization strategy and targeted poverty alleviation work.

4. Discussion

4.1 Conclusion of literature research

Through systematic literature research, we draw the following conclusions, which lay a theoretical foundation for the subsequent empirical analysis:

- 1) Volunteering experience has accumulated social capital and practical experience for college students, and enhanced their willingness to start a social enterprise.
- 2) Innovation and entrepreneurship education and social support systems play a crucial role in the transformation of volunteers into social entrepreneurs.
- 3) College volunteers' personal characteristics (such as social responsibility and innovation ability) significantly affect their willingness and ability to transform.

The results of these literature studies not only deepen our understanding of the transformation process of college volunteers into social entrepreneurs, but also provide important theoretical support.

4.2 Conclusion of case study

Through the in-depth analysis of these typical cases, we draw several important conclusions:

1) Volunteer service experience lays the foundation: Participating in volunteer service enables college students to accumulate rich social experience and interpersonal resources, which provides strong support for their subsequent social entrepreneurship.

2) Integration and utilization of social resources: Successful social entrepreneurship projects can often effectively integrate resources from all walks of life and obtain support from enterprises, governments, non-profit organizations and other parties.

3) Innovative thinking and execution: College students' innovative thinking and strong execution in the project are the key factors to promote the success of the project.

These conclusions not only provide a valuable empirical basis for understanding the transformation path of college volunteers to social entrepreneurs, but also provide a successful model and lessons for other colleges and young entrepreneurs.

5. Conclusion

Based on the above research results, through the inductive reasoning method, we will summarize the key factors and typical practices of young university student volunteers in Zhejiang Province's transition to social entrepreneurship, and construct the countermeasures and path framework for application-oriented undergraduate students in Zhejiang Province to train young volunteers who are aspiring to transform into social entrepreneurs.

5.1 Focus on improving your ability in the field of social entrepreneurship and improve your professional quality:

First of all, we should identify our own advantages and interests. Each young volunteer has his or her own unique skills and passions. Find his or her interest and combine it with public welfare to form a public welfare brand with his or her own characteristics. Secondly, focus on team building and resource integration. A successful social entrepreneurship project is often inseparable from an efficient team and sufficient resources. Therefore, social entrepreneurs transformed from young volunteers need to learn how to build and manage a team, as well as how to raise funds, materials and other resources. Finally, it is crucial to maintain an attitude of innovative thinking and continuous learning. The public welfare sector also needs innovation and change. Only by constantly innovating can we attract more people's attention and support. Therefore, young volunteers should dare to try new methods and ideas and break through the limitations of traditional frameworks during their transformation into social entrepreneurs.

5.2 The government should provide support and guidance to promote win-win cooperation among all sectors of society:

Relying on relevant policies issued by Zhejiang Province, such as the Implementation Opinions on Accelerating the Development of Mass Maker Space to Promote Entrepreneurship and Innovation, actively promote the transformation and development of colleges and the reform of innovation and entrepreneurship education. First, colleges can establish or participate in the alliance of entrepreneurship colleges to achieve resource-sharing and complementary advantages and jointly promote social entrepreneurship education. Second, the government can reduce the threshold and cost of social entrepreneurship by formulating preferential policies, such as tax relief, financial support, project subsidies, etc. At the same time, a special fund for social entrepreneurship should be established to provide start-up capital and operational support to interested young volunteers, and encourage them to turn their creativity and enthusiasm into practical actions. Finally, in-depth cooperation between schools and enterprises should be actively promoted to provide more opportunities for students to practice social entrepreneurship. Encourage the combination of volunteer service and public welfare projects, discover social problems through volunteer service activities, and inspire students' inspiration for social entrepreneurship.

5.3 Colleges should integrate resources inside and outside the university to jointly support the development of students' social entrepreneurship projects

First, colleges can cultivate students' sense of innovation and social responsibility by setting up special courses and workshops on social entrepreneurship. These courses can cover the planning, execution and management of

public welfare projects, allowing students to learn and master relevant knowledge in practice. At the same time, colleges can invite successful public interest entrepreneurs to share their experiences and stimulate students' enthusiasm for entrepreneurship. Secondly, colleges should encourage students to participate in social practice, so that they can go out of campus and go into every corner of the community and society to learn about social needs and problems. Through this hands-on experience, students can better understand the importance and urgency of public welfare undertakings, laying a solid foundation for their future social entrepreneurship. Finally, build a platform to promote the integration of public welfare resources inside and outside the university. Jointly promote the implementation of public welfare projects. This will not only expand the impact of public welfare projects, but also provide students with more practical opportunities.

Through the implementation of the above countermeasures and paths, Zhejiang applied undergraduate can effectively train a group of young volunteers who are aspiring to transform into social entrepreneurs. These young volunteers not only have solid professional knowledge and strong practical ability, but also have a strong sense of social responsibility and mission, and can play an important role in the future social reform. At the same time, this will also promote the vigorous development of social entrepreneurship in Zhejiang Province and even the whole country.

6. Prospects and Shortcomings

Although we have some preliminary research on the transformation of young college volunteers into social entrepreneurs, there are still some problems and shortcomings that need to be solved. First of all, in terms of empirical research, although this study is explored through literature research and case analysis, these studies are often limited to specific regions or specific types of projects, and lack universality and representativeness. In addition, this study only uses qualitative methods, and does not use quantitative methods to verify and explore analysis.

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